

A Guideline for Image Compression in Earth Science

The **purpose** of this guideline is to describe essential parameter choices when compressing marine images (photos and videos) for scientific use.

The **goal** of this document is to raise awareness of various encoding parameters, their impact on quality and file size, and to assist in selecting appropriate parameters when creating or converting images.

The **scope** of this guideline applies to the encoding of digital marine images captured by cameras and recording systems for scientific purposes.

Adhering to the guideline will **result** in pristine images where the encoding parameters are tailored to the research purpose of the recording, without any unintended data loss or impact on the visual quality.

Introduction

The image captured by a camera sensor is not an unadulterated representation of reality. The light that reaches the camera sensor has already been influenced on the way through the camera system, e.g., affected by diffraction blur, chromatic and spherical aberrations, color filtering and rasterization.

After reading the sensor and digitizing the signal, the encoding process occurs. The selection of an appropriate codec and its parameters is crucial in determining whether additional distortions are introduced or avoided. Here, a trade-off needs to be struck between data reduction and data accuracy. While the former enables small file sizes by reducing the amount of data, resulting in lower storage costs and faster data transfer, the latter focuses on preserving information.

Lossy encoding introduces irreversible information loss, resulting in a degraded version of the source data, while lossless encoding preserves information and allows a perfect reconstruction. Both compression techniques aim to reduce data while creating a faithful duplicate.

Even though lossy encoding discards data irreversibly, it depends on the codec and encoding parameters if the effect is visible or not. Thus, setting the encoding parameters correctly, unintended visible data loss can be avoided despite having data reduction. On the other hand, disproportionate encoding parameters might result in huge files with visible artefacts.

Whether lossless or lossy, the main objective of image encoding is data reduction. The balance between data saving and data loss depends on the purpose of the recording as well as post-processing steps. It is influenced by the selection of containers, codecs and encoding parameters. To simplify the decision-making process, this guideline lists the most important media codec parameters and briefly explains their effects.

Photo / Still image encoding

The image sensor of digital cameras converts photons into electrical charge. Subsequently, the voltage is sampled and quantized into a digital signal.

This signal is referred to as a raw image and can be stored either uncompressed, lossless or lossy compressed via raw data formats. Further processing is subsequently applied, e.g., demosaicing, defective pixel removal, white balancing, noise reduction, gamma correction, color space conversion and optical corrections.

For photos, these modifications are either stored as sidecar files (i.e., XMP) next to the raw file, inside the raw file (i.e., DNG) or encoded to new image files, i.e., JPEG, TIFF.

The decision to capture images in raw format depends on the necessity to get a pristine source image with the best level of detail provided by the sensor, no matter of file size or compatibility. Furthermore, if post-processing steps should be applied, raw formats are ideal due to their high fidelity.

RAW File Format

There exists a wide range of proprietary raw data formats from diverse camera manufacturers, resulting in a non-consistent way of storing the data. This inconsistency has a direct impact on the ability to process raw images with software, as they require dedicated raw file readers. Furthermore, the development of these data formats depends on the camera manufacturer, they can evolve and get replaced over time. Most often, it is uncertain how future-proof they are.

The DNG (Digital Negative) file format is a standardized open-source raw file format, however only some camera manufacturer support shooting in DNG natively. Hence it is recommended to convert proprietary raw data formats into DNG, to ensure best compatibility over time.

Furthermore, it is recommended to store an extra image file next to the raw file, i.e., JPEG. This enhances compatibility with common media viewers and enables viewing without the necessity of additional processing, like luminance, color or optical corrections.

Processed Image Format

In order to reduce the storage size of image files, the raw data from the camera sensor is subjected to further processing. Following the digitalization of the sensor data, an image processing pipeline is applied, in which both the photographic rendering of the scene and the encoding of the media file takes place. This can be carried out either within the camera or externally, using a raw file converter.

The encoding process includes both the compression of the data by an encoder and its subsequent storage in a container. Compression can be either lossless or lossy, and is influenced by a number of encoding parameters, which affect the quality and file size.

In order to prevent the inadvertent loss of information while compressing, it is essential to select adequate codec and encoding parameters based on the acquisition purpose. Ideally, before shooting with the camera, the camera settings should be selected based on the expected motif so that they meet the needs. This will avoid unnecessarily large files or unintentional loss of information due to the wrong parameters being selected. However, due to the constraints of the recording system, cameras may have limitations regarding the control of information loss and data size. The following table provides an overview of photo parameters and how they affect the final image.

Photo Parameter	Information	Recommended	Not Recommended	Note
File Format	Lossless Codecs: Data compression without technical or visual information loss.	Lossless: PNG, TIFF	Uncompressed	For a comparison between lossless TIFF and lossy JPEG compression, see Figure 1 in the Appendix.
	Lossy Codecs:	Lossy:		

	Remove data irreversibly by removing non-perceivable information, hence technical data loss that is ideally not visible by human. More data savings and therefore smaller files than lossless codecs.	JPEG		The choice of the file format entails a trade-off between data reduction and fidelity.
Bit depth / Color depth	<p>Number of bits used during the quantization for each color component.</p> <p>For 8 bit, each color component (red, green, blue) can be described with $2^8 = 256$ values, resulting in a total of $256^3 = 16.8 \cdot 10^6$ colors.</p> <p>10 bit: $1024^3 = 1.1 \cdot 10^9$ colors 12 bit: $4096^3 = 68.7 \cdot 10^9$ colors</p>	Bit depth ≥ 8 bit		<p>For an example of how bit depth affects visual quality and data accuracy, see Figure 2 in the Appendix.</p> <p>Using a lower bit depth than provided by the camera sensor results in irreversible loss of information, however leads to data reduction and smaller file sizes.</p> <p>The maximum bit depth for JPEG is 8 bit, 16 bit for PNG and 32 bit for TIFF.</p> <p>For TIFFs with a bit depth greater than 8 bit, the selection of image viewers may be limited.</p>
Resolution	Width and height in pixel within the digital image.	Adequate to purpose		<p>Higher resolution can display more details but requires more storage. Additionally, they need more light to achieve the same signal-to-noise ratio as smaller resolutions for the same sensor size.</p> <p>Information loss due to downsampling or pixel binning is prevented when the image resolution matches the sensor resolution.</p> <p>The orientation of the images should match their content (landscape mode, portrait mode).</p>
Aspect Ratio		Native, 4:3, 3:2, 16:9		Information loss caused by sensor cropping can be avoided by setting the aspect ratio to match the native camera sensor aspect ratio.

Video / Moving image encoding

Video encoding is typically performed in real-time on camera and recording devices. However, due to limited computing capacity, licensing or policy reasons, manufacturers often perform a preselection regarding codecs and parameters. Nevertheless, for those that can be controlled by oneself, the following table provides an overview of their impact on data reduction and accuracy. When recording multiple videos consecutively, it is recommended to use identical video parameters. This ensures that the entire set can be processed in the same way later on.

Video Parameter	Information	Recommended	Not Recommended	Note
Container	A container defines the data structure in which the encoded video is stored, along with other data such as audio, metadata and subtitles.	MP4, AVI, MOV, MKV		Only add audio to the video container if intended. Otherwise, it is recommended to disable audio to prevent empty audio tracks in the video.
Codec Format	<p>Determines the way of compressing and decompressing video data, how the video is encoded and decoded.</p> <p>Lossy compression: Permanently removes data when encoding, can result in a reduced video quality. Creates smaller files.</p> <p>Lossless compression: No data and quality loss, resulting in large files but allowing a perfect reconstruction.</p>	<p>Lossy codecs: AVC (Advanced Video Codec, H.264) HEVC (High Efficiency Video Codec, H.265)</p>		<p>Lossless compression should only be used when it is crucial to preserve the exact visual information and quality degradation is not acceptable. In most cases, lossy encoding is sufficient and should be the preferred choice.</p> <p>Inter-frame codecs (consider neighboring frames during encoding) like H.264 / H.265 are more computational complex, however require less space than intra-frame codecs (encode every frame independently) like ProRes.</p>
Profile	The capabilities of the decoder defined by a set of features that can be used for video encoding, e.g., chroma format, bit depth. Ensures that the playback device has the ability to decode the video.	Automatically set by the encoder		Determined by the encoding parameters used.
Level	The capacity requirements of the decoder, defined by a set of restrictions, e.g. maximum bitrate, resolution and frame rate. Ensures that the playback device has enough performance to decode the video.	Automatically set by the encoder		Only relevant for playback systems that have limited performance.

Bitrate	Number of bits, required to store the information in the video, per time unit.	Automatically set by the encoder based on the bitrate mode and encoding approach (lossless or lossy).		<p>The higher the bit rate, the more information can be stored, but the larger the file size. The video size should be appropriate to the content of the video.</p> <p>Videos encoded at a constant bit rate may experience changes in perceived video quality during playback because the same number of bits are allocated over time, ignoring temporal or spatial complexity.</p>
Bitrate Mode	Determines how bits are allocated in the video.	Variable (VBR)		<p>VBR has a better tradeoff between quality and file size compared to CBR (constant bitrate).</p> <p>For lossy encoding, it is recommended to use the constant quality encoding mode CRF (=Constant Rate Factor). This mode uses a variable bitrate to allocate bits based on the temporal and spatial complexity inside the frame, achieving constant video quality.</p>
Width	Horizontal resolution of the video.	Width \geq 1920	Width < 1920	Higher resolutions require more storage space and are more computationally intensive to process than lower resolutions. In general, it is recommended to select a resolution that best serves the purpose of the video recording.
Height	Vertical resolution of the video.	Height \geq 1080	Height < 1080	
Scan Type	Specifies the order in which pixels are scanned in a frame.	Progressive (i.e., 1080p)	Interlaced (i.e., 1080i)	<p>For a comparison between interlaced and progressive scan type, see Figure 3 in the Appendix.</p> <p>Interlacing reduces the data rate via fields. It can cause unwanted image artifacts when played on digital displays and should be avoided. However, if a higher frame rate is required which is not available in progressive, a tradeoff must be made.</p>
Display Aspect Ratio (DAR)	Ratio between the width and height of the full image.	16:9 or same as camera sensor		<p>The most common aspect ratio for digital videos is 16:9.</p> <p>However, if sensor crop should be avoided, i.e., when it is crucial to capture everything in</p>

				<p>front of the camera, the native aspect ratio of the camera can be used.</p> <p>Aspect ratios that enhance immersion, such as 21:9, can be added in post-production and should not be used during shooting.</p>
Pixel Aspect Ratio (PAR)	Ratio between the width and height of the individual pixels.	1:1		Most digital systems use square pixels for displaying.
Frame rate / FPS	Frequency, at which consecutive frames are captured.	Frame rate ≥ 25	Frame rate < 23.976	<p>The human eye perceives a continuous stream of information rather than discrete frames. Higher frame rates are generally more noticeable in terms of smoothness, but the benefits decrease as the rate increases.</p> <p>A low frame rate can be useful in low light conditions due to increased exposure time, while a high frame rate is ideal for creating slow-motion videos.</p> <p>Standard broadcast framerate (based on the human perception):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Europe: 25 fps • America: 23.976 fps
Frame rate mode	Mode of frequency, at which consecutive frames are captured.	Constant (CFR)	Variable (VFR)	Most modern compression are based on constant frame rate (CFR). Variable frame rate (VFR) can cause issues during further processing, i.e., with editing software. However, when recording a VFR source and frame rate conversion should be avoided, a variable frame rate mode might be required.
Color model	Mathematical representation of colors in a video.	YUV		<p>The process of the YUV color space conversion introduces data loss. However, it can achieve an imperceptible data reduction when combined with chroma subsampling.</p> <p>In contrast, the RGB color space model is intended for lossless video formats or if high fidelity is important.</p>
Chroma subsampling	Video compression technique that makes use of the human visual	4:2:0		For the YUV color model, higher chroma subsampling than 4:2:0, such as 4:2:2 or

	system and reduces the amount of color information in encoded images, while preserving the luminance information.			4:4:4, are only meaningful when preserving color information during encoding is crucial. Especially, when extracting information from individual color channels or if the video is intended for post-processing.
Bit depth / Color depth	The number of bits used for each color value per pixel. The larger, the more colors and therefore information can be stored. However, at the cost of a larger file size.	Bit depth \geq 8 bit		<p>Post-processing steps and the playback system may affect the selected bit depth.</p> <p>More than 10 bits should rarely be needed.</p>

Appendix

Figure 1: Information fidelity during image compression.

Comparison of lossy jpeg compression with lossless tiff compression. The stronger the jpeg compression, the more information is irreparably lost and the more encoding artifacts, i.e., blockiness, appear.

Source: Adapted from [1].

Figure 2: Impact of bit depth reduction.

The bit depth has a direct impact of the visible details. With decreasing bit depth, the details get lost. The 1 bit image contains a color palette with 2^1 colors, the 2 bit image 2^2 colors, and the 24 bit image 2^{24} colors, respectively. Consequently, the latter contains three color channels (RGB) with 2^8 (=256) values each.

Source: Adapted from [2].

Figure 3: Interlaced and progressive scan type.

Comparison of interlaced and progressive scan type. In interlaced videos, moving objects show up with horizontal patterns on progressive monitors, i.e., digital displays, because two interlaced fields are displayed in one frame.

Source: Adapted from [3].

Figure: Sources

[1] Leys, Sally P; Federwisch, Luisa (2024): Ultrastructure micrographs of Antarctic deep-water sponges collected for microbiome study during expedition JR17003a in the western Weddell Sea [dataset]. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.966335>, In: Federwisch, Luisa; Leys, Sally P; Janussen, Dorte; Linse, Katrin; Hentschel, Ute; Busch, Kathrin (2024): Images and microbiome data of Antarctic deep-water sponges (Demospongiae and Hexactinellida) collected during expeditions PS96 and JR17003a in the Weddell Sea, Antarctica [dataset bundled publication]. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.965868>

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- Krämmer, C., Schoening, T. (2024). A Guideline for Video Compression for the Web in Earth Science. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11634187>

Glossary:

- AVC / H.264:** **Advanced Video Coding**, also known as **H.264** - standard for video compression.
- AVI:** **Audio Video Interleave** - digital multimedia container format developed by Microsoft.
- CBR:** **Constant Bit Rate** – video encoding mode where the encoder allocates a fixed amount of bits to achieve a constant bitrate throughout the video.
- CRF:** **Constant Rate Factor** – video encoding mode that adjusts the compression for each frame to receive a constant level of perceived quality for the entire video.
- DNG:** **Digital Negative** - digital, open, lossless raw image format.
- FPS:** **Frames Per Second** – referring to the framerate, which is defined as the number of consecutive frames per second that should be played back from a video file.
- HEVC / H.265:** **High Efficiency Video Coding**, also known as **H.265** - standard for video compression.
- JPEG:** **Joint Photographic Experts Group** – lossy digital image format for bit depths up to 8 bit per color channel.
- MKV:** **Matroska Video** - open standard digital multimedia container format developed by Matroska.org.
- MOV:** QuickTime **Movie**- digital multimedia container format developed by Apple.
- MP4:** Digital multimedia container format developed by MPEG and ISO.
- PAR:** **Pixel Aspect Ratio** – also known as sample aspect ratio, is the ratio between width and height of a pixel. Most modern videos have a square PAR (1:1).
- PNG:** **Portable Network Graphics** – lossless digital image format for bit depths up to 16 bit per color channel.
- RGB:** **Red Green Blue** – additive color space that is based on the human perception of color, which is characterized by three types of cones: red, green and blue.
- TIFF:** **Tagged Image File Format** – lossless digital image format for bit depths up to 32 bit per color channel.
- VBR:** **Variable Bit Rate** – video encoding mode where the encoder allocates bits variably, allowing higher bitrates for complex scenes and lower bitrates for simple scenes.
- XMP:** **Extensible Metadata Platform** - standard for creation, processing and interchange of metadata.
- YUV:** Color space that considers the luminance and color perception of the human visual system. The human eye is more sensitive to brightness than to color, thus separating the luma component (**Y**) from the two chroma components, blue-difference (**U**) and red-difference (**V**), allows the chroma components to be reduced independently of the luminance.

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- Abstract:** This guideline document describes important photo and video encoding parameters that affect file size, quality, data accuracy, and thus the scientific potential of acquired image data. It aims to enable scientists to encode the best image data for their use cases.
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